

Port of Santa Cruz de Tenerife (ES)

This fiche includes maps displaying the location of the sampling points (SPOs) around the port of Santa Cruz de Tenerife (ES) with measurements of NO₂ and PM_{2.5} in 2023 (E1a validated data AQ e-Reporting). The tables include additional information on the annual mean concentrations of each SPO with available data (data coverage larger than 75%), distances of the SPOs from the port area, location of the SPO in one of the 8 wind sectors around the port (WS: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW), population living in the WS within 10 km from the port, and trends of annual mean concentrations (2005-2023) when available. The presented information is based only on SPOs reported to the EEA, additional SPOs or data may exist at national level.

Port of Santa Cruz de Tenerife (ES)

Port area and NO₂ air quality SPOs around the port within 5 and 10 km

Port area and PM_{2.5} air quality SPOs around the port within 5, 10 and 20 km

Pozzoli, L., Gressent, A., Soares, J., Colette, A., Monge, S. & González Ortiz, A. (2025). Air quality around ports (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2024/12, version 2, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17416089>).
[ETC HE Report 2024/12: Air quality around ports — Eionet Portal](#)

NO₂ SPOs in 2023 around the port

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Spain	ES2000A	Industrial	28.46	-16.26	22.01		1.14	SW	176,511
Spain	ES1131A	Industrial	28.46	-16.26	14.89		1.16	SW	176,511
Spain	ES2021A	Industrial	28.46	-16.26	11.88		1.43	SW	176,511
Spain	ES2020A	Industrial	28.46	-16.27	16.62		1.97	SW	176,511
Spain	ES2003A	Background	28.46	-16.28	12.87		2.46	SW	176,511
Spain	ES1976A	Industrial	28.46	-16.28	12.46		2.49	SW	176,511
Spain	ES1759A	Industrial	28.45	-16.28	23.36		2.63	SW	176,511
Spain	ES1975A	Background	28.46	-16.28	11.06		2.65	SW	176,511

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PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 1)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Spain	ES2000A	Industrial	28.46	-16.26	15.20		1.14	SW	176,511
Spain	ES1131A	Industrial	28.46	-16.26	10.71		1.16	SW	176,511
Spain	ES2021A	Industrial	28.46	-16.26	17.88		1.43	SW	176,511
Spain	ES2020A	Industrial	28.46	-16.27	10.54		1.97	SW	176,511
Spain	ES1976A	Industrial	28.46	-16.28	7.13	-2.15	2.49	SW	176,511
Spain	ES1759A	Industrial	28.45	-16.28	9.12		2.63	SW	176,511
Spain	ES1975A	Background	28.46	-16.28	10.66		2.65	SW	176,511
Spain	ES1772A	Industrial	28.39	-16.36	10.26		12.57	SW	176,511
Spain	ES1756A	Industrial	28.38	-16.36	11.04		13.99	SW	176,511
Spain	ES2022A	Industrial	28.38	-16.37	9.28		14.24	SW	176,511

PM_{2.5} SPOs in 2023 around the port (Part 2)

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from port area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Population in WS and 10 km from port
Spain	ES1764A	Industrial	28.38	-16.37	6.51		14.51	SW	176,511

